

ABOUT PHONETICS SECTIONS AND INTERNAL FEATURES AND PHONOLOGY IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article provides extensive information about the phonological layer in English, the specific types of the linguistic Department of phonology, phonetic units. In addition, examples are given through scientific analyzes on the units that make up phonetics. This article scientifically covers the phonetic features of the English language. The rules were cited and scientifically explained.*

Keywords: *phonetics, phonology, dialect, contraction, sound, vowel, consonant.*

Introduction

Phonological analysis of English often focuses on one or more prestige or standard accents, such as the adopted Pronunciation for England, General American for the United States, and General Australian (Australia), or uses it as a reference point. Nevertheless, many other dialects of the English language are spoken, which developed independently of these standardized accents, particularly regional dialects. Information about this standardized accent serves as a limited guide to all English phonology, which can later be expanded upon familiarization with many other dialects of the English language.

A phoneme of a language or dialect is an abstraction of a speech sound or a group of different sounds, all of which are perceived by speakers of the same language or dialect as having the same function. For example, through English, the word consists of three phonemes: the initial sound “th”, the sound “r” and the vowel sound. Phonemes in these and many other English words do not always come directly to the letters used in their writing (English spelling is not as strong phonemic as in other languages). The number and distribution of phonemes in the English language varies from dialect to dialect, and also depends on the interpretation of the individual researcher. The number of consonant phonemes is usually put 24 (or a little more, depending on the dialect). The number of vowel sounds can change more; The system presented on this page contains 20-25 vowels in the Received Pronunciation, 14-16 in the common American, and 19-21 vowels in Australian English. The pronunciation keys used in dictionaries usually contain a little more characters than this to account for some significant differences that may not be phonemic, more strictly speaking, of certain sounds used in foreign words.

If the organs of speech (tongue, lips, teeth, alveoli) close up so that they completely block the passage for air, then we pronounce the occlusive consonant. Such consonants are also called explosive, since a small explosion is heard when the speech organs are opened. The consonants [p, b, t, d, k, g] belong to the stop plosive sounds. If air passes out through the nasal cavity, then such occlusive sounds are called nasal sounds. Examples of nasal occlusive sounds are [n, m, ŋ]. If the organs of speech do not close completely, but leave a narrow passage - a gap for air, then we pronounce a slit consonant. In English, slit sounds are [θ, p, s, z, h, f, v, w, r, j, l]. Among the consonants, there are slotted sounds. They are called so because the opening of the barrier occurs slowly; the complete obstruction passes into the slit. These are the sounds [t, d]. An obstruction in

the path of exhaled air can be formed by various organs of speech. If the lower lip approaches the upper lip, then labial consonants appear. These are the sounds [p, m, w]. If the lower lip touches the upper teeth, then such consonants are called labiodental. These are the sounds [f, v]. If the tip of the tongue is between the lower and upper front teeth, then the interdental consonant is pronounced:

English consonants [t, d, l, s, z] are alveolar, since the tip of the tongue touches or rises to the alveoli, in contrast to Russian, dental consonants, since the end of the tongue rises to the inner surface of the upper teeth. According to the work of the vocal cords, deaf and voiced consonants are distinguished. When pronouncing voiceless consonants, the glottis is opened and the exhaled air passes through the larynx silently. With voiced consonants, the vocal cords are drawn together and tense. The exhaled air causes them to vibrate, resulting in a voiced consonant sound. In English, voiced sounds include: [b, v, g, d, z, l, m, n, r], voiceless sounds - [k, p, s, t, f, θ, h].

To classify vowels, various positions of the tongue relative to the hard palate are considered, as well as which part of the tongue is involved in articulation and how high the back of the tongue rises to the hard palate. Vowels of the front row are distinguished, when the tip of the tongue rests against the base of the lower teeth, and the back of the tongue is quite close to the hard palate: the vowel [i:].

If the tongue is pulled back and the tip of the tongue is lowered, and the back of the tongue is raised to the soft palate, we pronounce the back vowels: the English sound [a:]. The quality of the vowel depends on the tension of the muscles of the speech organs: the more intense the articulation, the clearer and brighter the sound. Accordingly, a distinction is made between tense and non-tense vowels. For example, the English vowel [i:] is pronounced with more tension than [i]. Thus, we see how diverse the phonetic structure of the English language is. But much also depends on the correct pronunciation and its features, which is described in the next section of this work. In English, articulation, i.e. pronunciation of vowels is almost unaffected by consonants. The vowel sound is the leading one in articulation. In this regard, it is recommended to combine as many different consonants as possible with the vowel when setting the English pronunciation. So, we examined the features of the pronunciation of English sounds. The next skill needed is to label them in writing. This is what the next section is about. Transcription Transcriptions are special characters that represent actual spoken speech sounds. The need to master transcription is due to the discrepancy between spelling and pronunciation in English. There are a large number of words that have either unreadable letters or exceptions to the rule. In the English pronunciation system, there are 48 sounds, therefore, there are 48 transcription symbols. Two vertical dots after the vowel in the transcription indicate the longitude of the sound.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

English, like other Germanic languages, has a particularly large number of vowel phonemes, and in addition, vowels in English differ significantly in dialects. Consequently, the corresponding vowels can be transcribed with different characters depending on the dialect in question. When we consider English as a whole, lexical sets are often used, each of which is referred to by a word containing the corresponding vowels or vowels. For example, the LOT set is made up of words that have /ɑ/ in the Received Pronunciation as lot and /ɑ/ in the General American language. Then the "LOT vowel" refers to the vowel sound that appears in these words, regardless of which dialect it is considered, or (at a more abstract level) the diaphoneme that represents this dialectal correspondence. John C. A common system of lexical sets developed by

Wells is listed below; the corresponding phonemes for RP and General American for each set are given using the characters used on this page.

Phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies the nature of speech sounds and provides methods for their statement, classification, imitation. It is associated with the telling of cheerful speech sounds in the language of the world. It is a system that imitates sounds in linguistics. These units are called phonemes. Phonetics is a scientific study of speech sounds, which consists in describing and classifying human sounds, understanding the creation of sounds, comparing and comparing sounds diagonally.

DISCUSSION

The branches of phonetics consist of three main sub-areas in terms of sound generation (articulation), transmission (acoustic) and perception (auditive). Three classifications of sounds must be recognized initially: telephones (human sounds), phonemes (units that distinguish meaning in language), allophones (units without distinction).

The traditional way of describing speech sounds depends on the movements of the vocal organs that form them. Important in the formation of speech the main structures, which are the lungs and the respiratory system, together with the vocal organs shown in Figure 1, the flow of air from the lungs passes between the vocal cords, which are two small muscle folds located in the larynx. at the top of the windpipe. The space between the vocal cords is called glottis. The distance of the vocal cords from each other, when breathing normally, the air emanating from the lungs passes freely in relation to the pharynx (see Figure 1) and the oral cavity. But if the sound is tuned in such a way that there is a narrow passage in the middle of the vocal cords, the air flow will cause them to be absorbed together. As soon as they are together, there is no air flow, and the pressure under them increases until they disintegrate again. Then the air flow between them causes them to be sucked together again and the vibration cycle continues. The sounds that are formed in the vibration of the vocal cords are called Audible, unlike the sounds in which the vocal cords are separated from each other, they are called Muted.

Results

The airways above the vocal cords are called the vocal tract in general terms. Phonetically, they can be divided into the oral route within the oral cavity and pharynx, and the nasal passage within the nose. Most speech sounds are characterized by the movement of the lower articulators, that is, the tongue or lower lip, towards the upper articulators inside the oral cavity. The upper surface contains several important structures in terms of speech production, such as the upper lip and upper teeth; The alveolar ridge is a small tumor located behind the upper front teeth, which can be easily felt with the tongue. The main part of the roof of the mouth is formed by a hard palate at the front and a soft palate or velum at the back.

The soft palate is a muscle flap that can be raised to close the nasal passages and prevent air from escaping through the nose. Velic closure is called when the soft palate is raised enough to press against the back wall of the pharynx. At the lower end of the soft palate there is a small hanging insert called the uvula.

Stops involve closing articulators to impede air flow. This method of articulation can be considered from the point of view of nasal and oral stops. If the soft palate goes down, the air can still escape through the nose, a nasal stop is called. Sounds like this come at the beginning of my and close words. If, in addition to the articular closure in the oral cavity, the soft palate rises and the nasal passages are blocked, then the flow of air is completely blocked, the pressure in the

mouth increases, and a stop of the mouth occurs. formed. When the articulators are opened, the air flow is released with explosive quality. Such a sound is found in consonants in the words pie, tie, kye, buy, die, guy. Many administrators call these two joints nasal, namely nasal stops (closure of articulators in the oral cavity) and stops, i.e. mouth stops (elevation of the soft palate to form a Velic closure).

The fricative sound involves the approach of two articulators, so that the air flow is partially obstructed and a turbulent air flow is formed. The mechanisms used in the production of these sounds can be compared to the physical forces involved when the wind "whistles" the angle. For example, the head sounds in the words fie, number, sigh, shame. Some organs divide into slotted and grooved fricatives or rill and flat fricatives, depending on the form of compression in the oral cavity required to form fricatives. Other administrators divide fricatives into sibilants such as sighs and shyness, and nonsibilants such as fie and son.

CONCLUSION

Having studied the literature on this topic, we can formulate some conclusions. And the first thing I would like to draw your attention to is the definition of phonetics. Phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies the sounds of speech and the sound structure of the language. In phonetics, categories such as the classification of sounds, their pronunciation, logical stress and intonation are considered. The purpose of the work was realized, since the most significant and necessary phonetic rules and features were identified in it. Having studied this topic, I deepened my knowledge in this area and turned my attention to some aspects that were unknown to me before starting work. In the future, I plan to study the methodology of teaching English in primary and secondary schools. The materials of this research work can be useful to all people who are just starting to learn the language, as well as to everyone who wants to deepen their knowledge of the phonetic features of this foreign language.

Estimators

Estimators are formed when one articulator approaches another, but does not make the sound path so narrow that a turbulent air flow occurs. The terms Frictionless continue, half-vowel, and glide are sometimes used for some sounds made by such an articulation method. We and the consonants in your words are an example of an approximation.

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